

Safe Inspection and Maintenance supporting workers with modular robots, Artificial intelligence, and augmented Reality

Deliverable D8.1

Principles for impact assessment of SIMAR against SoEL requirements

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement N° 101070604.

Project Information

Grant Agreement Number	101070604
Starting Date	01/09/2022
Duration	36 months
Call Identifier	HORIZON-CL4-2021-DIGITAL-EMERGING-01
Topic	HORIZON-CL4-2021-DIGITAL-EMERGING-01-10
Project Website	www.simar-project.eu
Project Coordinator	Miguel Ángel Trujillo
Organisation	Fundación Andaluza para el Desarrollo Aeroespacial (CATEC)
Email	matrujillo@catec.aero

Document Information

Due date: 31/10/2023	Submission date: 31/10/2023
Lead beneficiary:	CATEC
Work Package	WP8
Main Editor(s)	CATEC
Contributor(s)	CATEC, CHEVRON
Reviewer (s)	QUASSET

Document Classification					
Status	F	Nature	R	Dissemination level	PU
Draft: D		R: Document, report		PU = Public	
Final: F		DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc. DATA: Data sets, microdata, etc. DMP: Data management plan ETHICS: Deliverables related to ethics issues. SECURITY: Deliverables related to security issues OTHER: Software, technical diagram, algorithms, models, etc		SEN = Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement Classified R-UE/EU-R = EU RESTRICTED under the Commission Decision No2015/444 Classified C-UE/EU-C = EU CONFIDENTIAL under the Commission Decision No2015/444 Classified S-UE/EU-S = EU SECRET under the Commission Decision No2015/444	

Revision history			
Version	Issue Date	Status	Author(s)
0.1	19/09/2023	First Draft	CATEC
0.2	10/10/2023	Partners Contribution	QUASSET, CHEVRON
0.3	16/10/2023	Consolidated version	CATEC
0.4	24/10/2023	Partner review	QUASSET
1.0	31/10/2023	Final version	CATEC

Content

1.	INTRODUCTION.....	7
1.1.	Purpose of the document.....	7
1.2.	Scope of the document.....	7
1.3.	Structure of the document.....	7
2.	IDENTIFICATION OF THE SIMAR IMPACT SCENARIO	8
3.	IDENTIFICATION OF THE APPLICABLE SOEL REQUIREMENTS.....	9
3.1.	Identification of the applicable SoEL principles for the Data Protection and Privacy impact assessment.....	9
3.1.1.	GDPR definition [1]	9
3.2.	European and national regulation on Unmanned Aerial Vehicles	11
3.3.	Artificial Intelligence European framework.....	13
3.4.	Regulatory Sandbox	14
3.5.	ATEX Certification	15
3.6.	X-Ray equipment regulation	17
3.6.1.	Spanish X-Ray Equipment Regulation.....	17
3.6.2.	French X-Ray Equipment Regulation	18
4.	GUIDELINES FOR THE IMPACT ASSESSMENT.....	19
4.1.	Guidelines for the impact assessment in Social Aspects.....	20
4.1.1.	GDPR	20
4.2.	Guidelines for the impact assessment in Ethical Aspects.....	21
4.2.1.	AI ACT [5].....	21
4.3.	Guidelines for the impact assessment in Legal Aspect.....	22
4.3.1.	European Drone Regulation.....	22
4.3.2.	ATEX	23
4.3.3.	X-Ray regulation.....	24
4.4.	Guidelines for the impact assessment which applies to SIMAR Impact Scenario.....	26
5.	IMPACT ASSESSMENT METHODOLOGY	26
5.1.	SoEL Impact Assessment Identification	27
5.2.	SoEL Impact Assessment Analysis.....	27
5.3.	SoEL Impact Assessment Evaluation and Treatment.....	28
6.	CONCLUSIONS.....	28
7.	REFERENCES.....	30

List of Figures

Figure 1. Subcategories within the Open category (source EASA) [4].....12

Figure 2. Zone delimitation for x ray inspection.....25

List of Tables

Table 1. Acronyms list.....5

Table 2. SIMAR Impact Scenarios8

Table 3. AI risk categories stated in the AI ACT regulation.....21

Table 5. Applicable SoEL requirements to each SIMAR Scenario26

Acronyms

Table 1. Acronyms list

Abbreviation	Description
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ASN	Nuclear Safety Authority
ATEX	ATmosphères EXplosives
BOE	State official newsletter
BVLOS	Beyond Visual Line Of Sight
CAA	Civil Aviation Authority
CSN	Nuclear Safety Council
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EASA	European Union Aviation Safety Agency
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FCA	Financial Conduct Authority
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HSE	Health, Safety, and Environment
IA	Impact Assesment
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
I&M	Inspection and Maintenance
MEP	Member of the European Parliament
PEC	Pulse Eddy Current
PPE	Personal protective equipment
R&D	Research and Development
SoEL	Social, Ethical and Legal
STS	Standard Scenario

UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle
UAS	Unmanned Aerial System
UTM	Unmanned Traffic Management
VLOS	Visual Line Of Sight

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Purpose of the document.

Deliverable D8.1 of the SIMAR project concerns the SIMAR project's Social, Ethical, and Legal (SoEL) aspects.

The purpose of this document is to establish the SoEL principles that apply to the SIMAR project, in order to determine the standards that served as a benchmark for evaluating the project's actions and outcomes.

1.2. Scope of the document.

The current deliverable describes the important areas of applicable law and regulation, as well as operational guidelines for the ethical principles, in the context of the technologies that the SIMAR project aims to develop (autonomous vehicles, artificial intelligence), along with regard to data privacy and protection. This is done in order to give SIMAR partners a collection of significant ideas that they can use as a reference to evaluate the project's activity in the future, in relation to the relevant ethical and legal issues that have been highlighted.

1.3. Structure of the document.

This deliverable, D8.1 Principles for impact assessment of SIMAR against SoEL requirements, is divided into the following parts:

- Section 1 presents the purpose, scope and structure of the deliverable.
- Section 2 examines any potential changes in the SIMAR Impact Scenario in order to update the SoEL requirements and take into account the various types of use cases and any prospective changes in geography or legal implications.
- Section 3 offers a general overview of the applicable regulations for the development of novel technologies like artificial intelligence as well as updates the SoEL principles that apply for data protection and privacy impact, as well as European and national regulations for the operation of unmanned vehicles.
- Section 4 establishes the standards for the SIMAR Impact Scenario evaluation.
- Section 5 explains the Impact Assessment (IA) methodology that will be used in the SIMAR project to identify the activities that require an IA and how the evaluation, treatment, monitoring, and review of impacts will be carried out.
- Section 6 collects a summary of the main results from this document.

2. IDENTIFICATION OF THE SIMAR IMPACT SCENARIO

Identification of SIMAR Impact Scenario involve categorizing SIMAR Uses Cases according to scenario and type of developed robotic solution. In this regard, guidelines for the impact assessment have been established, taking into account all pertinent ethical, legal, and social data protection standards that apply to the project outcomes and activities with regard to their impact.

Table 2. SIMAR Impact Scenarios

SIMAR Scenario	SIMAR Use Case	Robot	Type of robotic solution	SIMAR Impact Scenario	Nº
Refineries	Refinery pipes inspection (Visual Inspection)	HYBRID	Aerial Vehicle (UAV)	Refineries - UAV	1
	Refinery pipes inspection (X-Ray)	HYBRID	Aerial Vehicle (UAV)	Refineries - UAV	2
	Refinery pipes inspection (PEC)	HYBRID	Aerial Vehicle (UAV)	Refineries - UAV	3

Since SIMAR technological developments have gone according to plan, the social, ethical, and legal aspects discussed in this deliverable D8.1 have also proven accurate. The SIMAR consortium has carried out an exhaustive investigation of the data that might have an impact on any of the specified SoEL requirements:

- **Social Aspects:** The use of onboard sensors that can collect environmental data and the participation of external participants in project activities (such as workshops, demonstration sessions or questionnaires) are both allowed by the applicable privacy and data protection framework. The on-board sensors in the SIMAR robotic systems that can cause a SoEL problem in terms of them collecting any private external data were carefully examined by SIMAR partners.
 - **Operational Camera.** A visual camera used to carry out the inspection, detecting infrastructure defects.
 - **Situational awareness camera.** A visual camera is employed to help the operator/inspector to localise the robot during the inspection process.
- **Ethical Aspects:** In terms of the ethical concern, the regulatory framework in effect is still that concerning cutting-edge novel technologies like Artificial Intelligence (AI).
- **Legal Aspects:** Regarding the legal aspect, the use of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles, operation in explosive atmospheres (ATEX), and the use of X-Ray equipment are all covered by the

applicable European legal and regulatory framework. This deliverable contains a detailed examination of this regulatory and legal environment.

In addition to the robotic systems and payloads, the Augmented Reality (AR) system of SIMAR will use the HoloLens 2 Industrial Edition, which is suitable for use in hazardous location environments (Class 1 – Division 2). This device integrates a variety of sensors, including inertial measurement units, optical and audio sensors, in order to provide effective tracking around an environment and enable multimodal interactions using gesture and gaze tracking. However, in the context of SIMAR, no sensitive data for the purpose of recognizing profiles or behaviours of individuals will be collected or stored by the AR system. Some biometric data may be stored locally on the device only if a user consents to biometric authentication (Iris Login). Being a commercial device, the HoloLens 2 complies with the EU data protection regulations and privacy directives (see Section 3).

3. IDENTIFICATION OF THE APPLICABLE SOEL REQUIREMENTS

The SoEL principles that apply to the SIMAR project's legal, data protection and privacy, and ethical issues are all described in this section.

3.1. Identification of the applicable SoEL principles for the Data Protection and Privacy impact assessment

The General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) [1] continues to be the primary relevant regulation for data protection in all SIMAR Project countries.

3.1.1. GDPR definition [1]

The main regulation framework regarding data protection in the European Union is Regulation 2016/679 on the protection of natural persons concerning the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data and repealing directive 95/46/EC, also known as GDPR.

The GDPR is applied to all processing of personal data relating to people residing in EU member states. It does not apply to the handling of personal information by "competent authorities for the purposes of the prevention, investigation, detection, or prosecution of criminal offenses, or the execution of criminal penalties," which expressly includes "the safeguarding against and prevention of threats to public security and the free movement of such data." The processing of solely domestic or personal activities without any ties to professional or commercial endeavors is also excluded. Last but not least, it excludes processing pertaining to actions not covered by Union legislation, such as those involving national security.

The GDPR defines specific personal data as information that is primarily related to a delicate or unusual component of a physical subject's personality, such as genetic, biometric, and health information.

Additionally, it is generally forbidden to process genetic data, biometric data used to uniquely identify a natural person, health data, or data pertaining to a natural person's sex life or sexual orientation. However, in some limited circumstances, it is permitted to process personal data that can reveal

racial or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, or trade union membership. Since they are regarded as the heart of the protection that citizens must be guaranteed by privacy legislation, these kinds of personal data are subject to special protections.

The EU Regulation does not apply to anonymous data. Whereas n. 26 declares that "The principles of data protection should therefore not apply to anonymous information, namely information which does not relate to an identified or identifiable natural person or to personal data rendered anonymous in such a manner that the data subject is not or no longer identifiable. This regulation does not therefore concern the processing of such anonymous information, including for statistical or research purposes".

The main regulatory actors concerned with privacy and data protection

Although being a European legislative initiative, Regulation 2016/679 defines the primary regulatory agencies at national level for the execution of data protection law. These take the form of National Data Protection Authorities (sometimes known as 'National Data Protection Commissioners')

Data roles

For the optimal development of the project, the SIMAR consortium, has defined the Data Roles that will apply to the project:

- Controller: "natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data; where the purposes and means of such processing are determined by Union or Member State law, the controller or the specific criteria for its nomination may be provided for by Union or Member State law"
- Processor: "a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes personal data on behalf of the controller".
- Data Protection Officer: According to Article 18 in the directive 95/46/EC, the "Personal Data Protection Officer" is responsible in particular for ensuring in an independent manner the internal application of the national provisions taken pursuant to the directive, and for keeping the register of processing operations carried out by the controller, containing the items of information referred to a register of processing operation notified shall be kept by the supervisory authority – thereby ensuring that the rights and freedoms of the data subjects are unlikely to be adversely affected by the processing operations. This natural person has been chosen by the SIMAR consortium due to professional qualities, in particular, specific understanding of the laws and practices addressing data protection" (art. 37, par. 5 GDPR). This information explained in more detail in deliverable D9.1 - OEI-Requirements N°1.

Legal Basis for the processing of personal data

According to Article 6 of the GDPR, processing of personal data must have a legal basis in order to be done so legally. Personal data may be processed for one of the following purposes in order to satisfy these requirements:

- The data subject has expressly consented.

- Processing is required to carry out a contract to which the data subject is a party or to take action at the request of the data subject prior to entering into a contract.
- Processing is required to satisfy a legal requirement to which the controller is subject.
- Processing is necessary to comply with another legal requirement.
- Processing is required in order to carry out a task in the public interest or in order for the controller or a third party to whom the data have been supplied to exercise official authority.
- Processing is required to protect the legitimate interests of the controller or the third party or parties to whom the data have been provided, unless those interests are exceeded by the protection of the data subject's fundamental rights and freedoms [2].

3.2. European and national regulation on Unmanned Aerial Vehicles

SIMAR Project must comply the European Drone Regulation, but also follows national and site-specific Drone Regulation.

The European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA) published Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2019/945 & Commission Implementing Regulation (EU) 2019/947 [3] on June 11, 2019, to ensure drone activities are safe and secure throughout Europe. The regulations would, among other things, enable the free movement of drones and a level playing field inside the European Union while assisting in safeguarding the security and privacy of EU people.

Both operational and technical requirements for drones are included in the new regulations. They outline the qualities a drone needs to possess in order to be flown safely, on the one hand. For instance, new drones will need to be individually recognizable, enabling law enforcement to locate a specific drone if needed.

The regulations, on the other hand, include all operation types, from those that don't need prior authorization to those that involve authorized operators and aircraft as well as the minimal training standards for remote pilots.

Although the EU legislation was released in June 2019, it did not go into effect until December 30, 2020. As a result, it is applicable whenever experiments or pilot tests are conducted.

Open category

For the “open” category, EASA has defined the following subcategories:

- A1: where it is possible to fly over people but not over assemblies of people.
- A2: fly close to people.
- A3: fly far from people.

UAS		Operation		Drone operator/pilot		
Max weight	Subcategory	Operational restrictions	Drone operator registration	Remote pilot competence	Remote pilot minimum age	
< 250 g	A1 (can also fly in subcategory A3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — No flight expected over uninvolved people (if it happens, overflight should be minimised) — No flight over assemblies of people 	No, unless camera / sensor on board and the drone is not a toy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — No training required 	No minimum age	
< 500 g			Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Read carefully the user manual — Complete the training and pass the exam defined by your national competent authority or have a 'Proof of completion for online training' for A1/A3 'open' subcategory 	16*	
< 2 kg	A2 (can also fly in subcategory A3)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — No flying over uninvolved people — Keep a horizontal distance of 50 m from uninvolved people 	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Read carefully the user manual — Complete the training and pass the exam defined by your national competent authority or have a 'Remote pilot certificate of competency' for A2 'open' subcategory 	16*	
< 25 kg	A3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Do not fly near or over people — Fly at least 150 m away from residential, commercial or industrial areas 	Yes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> — Read carefully the user manual — Complete the training and pass the exam defined by your national competent authority or have a 'Proof of completion for online training' for A1/A3 'open' subcategory 	16*	

Figure 1. Subcategories within the Open category (source EASA) [4]

Specific category

- Standard Scenario. The produced airborne platforms for the SIMAR project will fall into the "specific" category when operating in the petrochemical plants. There are two standard scenarios:
 - STS 1: VLOS operation in an urban environment but with ground-controlled area.
 - STS 2: BVLOS operation (until 2Km with observers) in a sparsely populated environment.

These two situations can only be used with drones that have the C5 and C6 labels as of January 2024. Up until that point, if any, national standard scenarios are applicable with some restrictions. For instance, the national standard scenario STS-01-ES in Spain only permits the flight of drones weighing up to 10 kg, not 25 kg as will be the case with drones with the C5 designation.

- Operational authorisation. This option requires to go through a complete authorisation process with the national aviation authority. Additionally, the organization that will serve as the drone operator must create a complete UAS operator structure and procedures, which has a significant impact on the amount of time and resources required. Positively, this method might not call for the deployment of a labelled drone, providing more flexibility and requiring less capital expenditure on the aerial platform to begin providing inspection services.

In this respect, related to the refinery scenario the Specific category applies to the Refinery UAV inspection use cases. The Specific category applies as a refinery is a non-fly-zone and only operations under the specific category are allowed.

3.3. Artificial Intelligence European framework

On 21st April 2021, the "Proposal for a REGULATION of the European Parliament and of the Council LAYING DOWN HARMONISED RULES on Artificial Intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act) [5] and AMENDING CERTAIN UNION LEGISLATIVE ACTS (the AI ACT)" was presented by the European Commission [6]. With this proposal, the European Union aims to advance on global AI legislation. With the publication of this directive, the EU made history as the first legislative body in the world to present a complete response in the form of proposed legislation focused exclusively on the development and implementation of AI [7]. Every AI system deployed in the EU will be subject to the rule, which has consequences for companies all over the world.

On 14th June 2023 the MEPs adopted Parliaments negotiating position on the AI ACT. In this new phase, talks will begin with European countries in the Council on the final form of the law. It is expected to reach an agreement before the end of this year.

According to the many uses of AI systems, the European Union's draft AI regulations classify the risk associated to AI into three main categories [8]. The AI Act ensure that AI developed and used in Europe is fully in line with EU rights and values including human oversight, safety, privacy, transparency, non-discrimination and social and environmental wellbeing [9].

1. Unacceptable-risk AI systems

Unacceptable risk of AI systems is the highest level of risk. This category restricts the use of AI in three instances. These applications include harmful subliminal, manipulative, or exploitative systems, remote biometric identification systems used by law enforcement in public places, and all kinds of social scoring.

2. High-risk AI systems

High-risk AI systems include a variety of systems that could have disturbing impacts on society. The European Union will evaluate and revise the high-risk AI systems. Systems for measuring social creditworthiness, recruitment or employee management systems, biometric identification in private areas, or systems for the administration of justice are included in these risks.

3. Limited and minimal-risk AI systems

In this section, chatbots, spam filters, customer and market segmentation systems, and virtually every other AI technology are categorized as having limited or minimal risk.

Depending on the level of risk, the proposed legislation recommends various restrictions for the AI systems developed. Unacceptable-risk AI systems will not be allowed in the European Union. Moreover, the High-risk systems will be subject to the largest range of requirements. Some of these requirements for companies using or offering these high-risk AI technologies are defined below:

- Implementation of a risk-management system.
- Data governance and management.
- Technical documentation.
- Record keeping and logging.
- Transparency and provision of information to users.

The draft regulation imposes the following supervisory duties on individuals that provide or utilize high-risk systems:

- Conformity assessments.
- Ensuring that these systems are explainable, monitorable and operate consistently throughout their lifetime.
- Establishing an organization-wide cyber risk management practice.

Finally, due to their low social impact and small risk, limited and minimal-risk AI systems will have fewer criteria. The majority of the specifications from this category will be connected to requirements regarding transparency. All risk categories will be subject to the set of requirements designed to raise awareness.

It is important to emphasize that since SIMAR AI systems do not manage personal data, its development will be under limited and minimal-risk (see Section 4.2.1). This results in an easy implementation of these technologies in the future.

3.4. Regulatory Sandbox

Recently, European governments have begun exploring a new policy instrument to validate emerging technologies and solutions. This instrument, known as the 'sandbox,' allows for testing without waiting for complete regulatory approval. The concept of the sandbox is inspired by playground enclosures filled with sand where children can experiment in a controlled environment. Similarly, the regulatory sandbox provides a delimited, safe, and controlled space for testing projects, solutions, or services without being hindered by existing rules [10].

Although there is no universally agreed definition, regulatory sandboxes can generally be described as schemes that enable firms to test innovations in a controlled real-world environment, following a specific plan developed and monitored by a competent authority. Regulatory sandboxes are a relatively new policy instrument, aiming to address regulatory challenges posed by technological advancements and the emergence of new products, services, and business models [11].

Initially adopted by the financial sector, the concept of the sandbox has gained traction. For instance, the UK's Financial Conduct Authority (FCA), which regulates financial services firms and markets, launched its Regulatory Sandbox in 2016. This initiative allows authorized and unauthorized firms, as well as technology businesses, to test innovative propositions in the market with real consumers. The sandbox offers benefits such as a controlled testing environment, reduced time-to-market, assistance in identifying consumer protection measures, and improved access to finance. Since August 2021, applications can be submitted at any time throughout the year [12].

The aerospace field has also embraced the regulatory sandbox. In April 2019, the UK's Civil Aviation Authority (CAA) established the Innovation Hub to support innovators in bringing new aviation and travel products and services to the market [13]. One of the instruments provided by the Innovation Hub is the Regulatory Sandbox, which operates through 'Challenges' proposed by the CAA or other entities. These Challenges, focusing on topics like Future Air Mobility and UTM (Unmanned Traffic Management), offer a pathway for approval to trial innovative solutions and shape future regulations. The Sandbox ensures that development activities address safety, security, and consumer protection risks associated with innovation [14].

At the European Union level, integrating the regulatory sandbox instrument in a comprehensive and unified manner has been more challenging. In November 2020, the Council published conclusions on regulatory sandboxes and experimentation clauses as tools for a forward-looking, resilient regulatory framework in the digital age. The Council urged the European Commission (EC) to facilitate an exchange of information and best practices on regulatory sandboxes between Member States and the Commission. The objectives were to assess the current state of regulatory sandboxes in the EU, explore experiences regarding their legal basis, implementation, and evaluation, and analyze how national sandbox initiatives can contribute to evidence-based policymaking at the EU level [15].

Responding to this request, the European Commission's Working Party on 'Better Regulation' presented an analysis on regulatory sandboxes in the 'Better regulation' toolbox report (November 2021). This document provides an overview of the sandbox concept, its relevance to policymaking, recent examples of regulatory sandboxes in the EU, and key considerations for their establishment. It emphasizes that existing sandboxes are limited to specific policy areas (e.g., financial services, energy, digital technologies) and are typically implemented locally to allow regulators greater control over the sandbox experiments. Scaling up sandbox results to the wider market is a major challenge, and at the EU level, there is a risk of market fragmentation if sandboxes for the same innovation are implemented without coordination among Member States. Regulators are aware of this risk and various approaches are being considered to mitigate it [11].

3.5. ATEX Certification

It is crucial to take into account how robotic systems will operate in environments with explosive atmospheres for all the inspection procedures in the oil and gas industry that have been taken into consideration, such as the SIMAR use cases associated with the refinery scenario.

The regulatory framework to this matter is the ATEX Directive 2014/34/EU, which covers equipment and protective systems intended for use in potentially explosive atmospheres. The directive defines the essential health and safety requirements and conformity assessment procedures, to be applied before products are placed on the EU market. It is aligned with the new legislative framework policy, and it is applicable from April 20th, 2016, replacing the previous Directive 94/9/EC [16].

This Directive shall apply to the following 'products' [17]:

- a. equipment and protective systems intended for use in potentially explosive atmospheres.
- b. safety devices, controlling devices and regulating devices intended for use outside potentially explosive atmospheres but required for or contributing to the safe functioning of equipment and protective systems with respect to the risks of explosion.
- c. components intended to be incorporated into equipment and protective systems referred to in point (a).

This Directive, as its precedent, establishes the criteria determining the classification of equipment-groups into categories, depending on the area of performance [17]:

1. Equipment-group I
 - a. Category M 1: intended for use in underground parts of mines as well as those parts of surface installations of such mines endangered by firedamp and/or combustible dust.
 - b. Category M 2: intended for use in underground parts of mines as well as those parts of surface installations of such mines likely to be endangered by firedamp and/or combustible dust.
2. Equipment-group II
 - a. Category 1: intended for use in areas in which explosive atmospheres caused by mixtures of air and gases, vapours, or mists or by air/dust mixtures are present continuously, for long periods or frequently.
 - b. Category 2: intended for use in areas in which explosive atmospheres caused by gases, vapours, mists, or air/dust mixtures are likely to occur occasionally.
 - c. Category 3: intended for use in areas in which explosive atmospheres caused by gases, vapours, mists, or air/dust mixtures are unlikely to occur or, if they do occur, are likely to do so only infrequently and for a short period only.

When a company performs a work on a refinery, there are two main approaches:

- Use ATEX-certified tools. ATEX certification is given to equipment that has gone through rigorous testing outlined by European Union directives and proved safe to use in specific environments with explosive atmospheres, according to the zone/s they are certified to be used in. Certification can be gained via notified bodies or through self-certification [18].

- Use hot work permits implementing emergency operational procedures. Due to the impossibility of applying ATEX to some equipment, Oil&Gas industry has started to design emergency operational procedures to use non-ATEX equipment in hazardous areas.

3.6. X-Ray equipment regulation

3.6.1. Spanish X-Ray Equipment Regulation

It is of paramount importance to thoroughly consider the operational aspects of X-ray equipment within the context of inspection procedures in the oil and gas industry. This careful consideration extends to various use cases, including those delineated in the SIMAR framework, particularly in scenarios related to refinery operations. Understanding the nuances of X-ray equipment utilization is pivotal for ensuring both efficiency and safety in these inspection procedures.

In order to align with the rigorous framework of Spanish legislation and harness X-ray equipment for industrial purposes, a comprehensive documentation process becomes imperative. This entails the meticulous preparation of technical documents that are an integral part of the authorization requisition for the operation of X-ray radiative facilities. These documents are meticulously crafted in adherence to guidelines provided by the Spanish Nuclear Safety Council (CSN). Importantly, while these guidelines are not mandatory, they serve as a foundational resource, offering invaluable guidance to all stakeholders involved in ensuring strict compliance with prevailing regulations concerning nuclear safety and radiological protection.

In the context of individuals professionally exposed to radiation, it's noteworthy that the exposure threshold stands at 50 mSv per year. For members of the general public, this limit is significantly lower, at just 1 mSv. In the specific project we are discussing, a stringent limit of 1 mSv has been established. Should one seek a comprehensive reference to all pertinent laws governing radioactive facilities, it can be found in the "Regulation on Nuclear and Radiative Facilities" (Royal Decree 1836/1999, BOE 31-12-1999). Through a careful review of Annex I of this regulation, it is possible to ascertain the categorization of our facility, which, in this case, belongs to category 3.

Both the aforementioned guide and the regulation share a common primary objective: safeguarding the radiological well-being of individuals in the presence of X-ray machines. This imperative necessitates that individuals working with such equipment are not subjected to harmful levels of radiation, ensuring their safety to the utmost degree feasible. Consequently, every individual working within the facility is mandated to carry a dosimeter, an indispensable tool for measuring and monitoring received radiation. However, it is vital to underscore that the authorization process must also encompass an estimation of the potential radiation dose that a worker might encounter during their duties.

Moreover, the regulation prescribes the deployment of various devices designed to monitor environmental radiation levels in real-time, especially in the event of equipment malfunctions or failures. It is incumbent upon those seeking authorization to furnish a comprehensive assessment of conceivable anomalous situations and outline the corresponding resolution strategies. This

comprehensive approach aligns with the regulation's stipulation for radiological protection measures within the facility, which necessitates the establishment of safety distances that effectively prevent radiation exposure to any individual. Justifying the appropriateness of these protective measures becomes a prerequisite for obtaining the authorization.

Additionally, the guide establishes the obligation to develop a detailed plan that delineates the process and frequency of equipment inspections within the facility. This plan encompasses safety systems, equipment, and instruments responsible for monitoring radiation levels. Furthermore, the plan meticulously outlines all aspects related to personnel, including the appointment of a supervisor and the designation of a facility manager.

Finally, to secure authorization, it is imperative to furnish an emergency plan that outlines the course of action in the event of an accident. Additionally, comprehensive information regarding the procedures for facility closure, with a keen focus on ensuring radiological safety conditions, must be included. This holistic approach underscores the unwavering commitment to maintaining the highest standards of safety and compliance within the realm of X-ray equipment utilization in industrial settings.

3.6.2. French X-Ray Equipment Regulation

In France, the regulation of nuclear sources activities, including radiography in industrial plants, is governed by stringent laws and guidelines aimed at ensuring the safety of personnel and the public. They can be lowered in cases where HSE risk mitigation can be proven. These regulations primarily focus on four main axes: licensing and authorization, radiation protection, training and qualification, and emergency preparedness.

1. Licensing and Authorization

The first axis revolves around the licensing and authorization process for facilities and individuals involved in activities with nuclear sources, including radiography. Owner must obtain a license from the French Nuclear Safety Authority (ASN) to use nuclear sources emitting radiations above given thresholds. This license outlines the specific conditions and safety measures they must adhere to. Individuals operating radiography equipment must also be authorized or declared as well as the equipment itself.

2. Radiation Protection

Ensuring the safety of personnel is paramount in the French regulatory framework. Strict radiation protection measures are in place to minimize exposure to ionizing radiation. These measures include establishing radiation protection zones, monitoring radiation levels, and implementing stringent control measures to limit exposure. Personal protective equipment (PPE), such as lead aprons and dosimeters, can be mandatory for workers in radiation areas depending on expected radiation level.

3. Training and Qualification

Personnel involved in radiography in industrial plants must undergo comprehensive training and qualification programs. These programs are designed to provide individuals with the necessary

knowledge and skills to safely handle nuclear sources and radiographic equipment. Training covers radiation safety, emergency procedures, and proper equipment operation. Certification is typically required to demonstrate competency.

4. Emergency Preparedness

Another critical aspect of the French regulation for nuclear sources activities is emergency preparedness. Industrial plants must have robust emergency plans in place to respond to accidents or incidents involving nuclear sources. This includes protocols for radiation alarms, evacuation procedures, and communication strategies with local authorities and the ASN. Regular drills and exercises are conducted to ensure readiness.

In addition to these four main axes, there are specific regulations related to the safe use of radiographic equipment:

Equipment Safety

Radiographic equipment must meet strict safety standards and undergo regular inspections. This includes ensuring the integrity of radiation sources, shielding, and control mechanisms. Equipment owners and operators are responsible for maintaining and regularly inspecting their devices.

Record-Keeping and Reporting

Comprehensive record-keeping and reporting are essential components of the regulatory framework. Facilities and individuals must maintain detailed records of radiation exposure, equipment maintenance, and safety assessments. These records are subject to inspection by the ASN.

Transport and Handling

The regulations also cover the safe transport and handling of nuclear sources. Specialized containers and transport procedures are required to minimize the risk of accidents during transportation. Handling and transportation companies, as well as employees, must be licensed and certified.

Public Awareness

Lastly, the French regulatory framework emphasizes public awareness and communication. Industrial plants are required to inform local communities about their activities involving nuclear sources. This transparency helps build trust and ensures that the public is aware of safety measures in place.

All aspects of the regulation aim to minimize the risks associated with ionizing radiation and ensure that nuclear activities, including radiography, are conducted safely, protecting both workers and the public. Compliance with these regulations is closely monitored and enforced by the ASN to maintain a high standard of safety in the nuclear industry.

4. GUIDELINES FOR THE IMPACT ASSESSMENT

This section explains the main detailed guidelines and regulations on how to conduct the impact assessment and make sure the project is developed according to the social, ethical and legal acceptance.

4.1. Guidelines for the impact assessment in Social Aspects

4.1.1. GDPR

As previously explained, the GDPR is the principal privacy and data protection regulation applied to all SIMAR countries.

At the time of writing this document, no modifications have been introduced to the project's framework. Then, an overview of the impact assessment guidelines is reminded.

SIMAR has two potential methods for collecting data from external participants:

Data collected from participants in project activities. The project involves the participation of humans in various activities like workshops, surveys or pilot demo sessions.

Data capture from the on-board sensors. In order to set the applicable principles for the SIMAR impact scenario, the type of data captured by each of the on-board sensors that may pose a SoEL issue (see section 2) has been analysed:

- **Operational camera.** This type of sensor can collect images. Within the SIMAR framework it will be used for a dual purpose:
 - **Detailed inspection.** The purpose is to inspect defects or infrastructure components, and the lens is set up for a short scope. The camera can only detect what is close to the lens and blurs distant items in this configuration. Then, even if there was a person in the proximity of where the inspection was taking place, no personal data could be collected. Furthermore, it is critical to mention that this camera will only record the photos specified by the operator/inspector, which will be focused exclusively on the problems to be evaluated.
 - **General inspection.** The purpose is to examine the infrastructure, and the lens type has been set up for wide coverage. This camera will be used to get a broad picture of the facility and scan for any major vulnerabilities, allowing it to see what's around the infrastructure. However, only pictures of the infrastructure that the operator or inspector has already designated will be captured. Then, any personal information would be gathered, regardless of whether a person was around when the inspection was taking place.
- **Situational awareness camera.** This type of sensor can collect images. The situational awareness camera, on the other hand, will act as a support to assist the operator/inspector place the robotic vehicle in relation to the infrastructure that has to be inspected. There will be no data collected in the image, which will only be focused on the drone's components and infrastructure.

Furthermore, it's critical to note that no external people are planned to visit the area during the missions and that the scenarios during the pilot experiments would be limited. Additionally, neither during the technical aspects of the project nor even in upcoming exploitation operations employing

SIMAR technologies is it anticipated that any personal data will be collected. Nonetheless, the GDPR must be taken in account if personal data is gathered.

Then and following the GDPR, when personal data will be collected from external participants:

- Informed consent procedures must be defined and implemented.
- The access to the data collected must be restricted only to authorised personnel.
- Nothing of the provided personal data will be handled out to third parties.
- A Data Project Officer (DPO) must be selected.

4.2. Guidelines for the impact assessment in Ethical Aspects

In regard to ethics, the primary applicable regulatory framework is associated to AI technologies. The European Commission is currently developing a proposal for an AI Regulation, with the objective of safeguarding the protection of fundamental rights and user safety, as well as trust in the development and adoption of AI.

Considering the ethical implications, the primary principle to be followed is summarized in the AI ACT published by the EC [9].

4.2.1. AI ACT [5]

The main proposal for the EU IA legislation was released on 21st July 2021. According to the new AI ACT proposed by the European Commission, this regulation includes three major categories in which risks might be defined. These three major hazards are discussed and evaluated in relation to the SIMAR project in the table below.

Table 3. AI risk categories stated in the AI ACT regulation

Type of risk	EU requirements	AI risk in SIMAR project
Unacceptable risk	Unacceptable-risk AI Systems will not be allowed in the European Union. Must be avoid.	Since the activities performed in the operation of the SIMAR I&M platform are focused on the inspection of defect infrastructures without involving people, none of the tasks performed by the SIMAR solution involve an unacceptable AI risk. The project's AI algorithms will not be subliminal, manipulative, or exploitative, and will not cause harm or remote biometric identification.
High risk	A large set of requirements will be applied to the High-risk systems:	Similarly, none of the SIMAR solution's duties provide a significant level of AI danger.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Implementation of a risk-management system. • Data governance and management. • Technical documentation. • Record keeping and logging. • Transparency and provision of information to users. 	<p>The implementation of the project's AI algorithms does not include social creditworthiness evaluation systems, recruiting or employee-management systems, biometric identification in non-public locations, or systems employed in judicial administration.</p>
<p>Limited and minimal risk</p>	<p>Transparency obligations.</p>	<p>Since there is not a specific field of application specified for I&M or autonomous navigation deployment of Artificial Intelligence, the category that best fits the purpose of the SIMAR Project belongs to "Limited and minimal risk AI Systems" and can be related to "Most other AI systems."</p> <p>SIMAR is committed to monitoring the algorithms produced within the project framework and their possible applications, ensuring that they meet all transparency obligations and remain in this category.</p>

SIMAR will develop an AI system for inspection analytics that will be integrated into all its robotic solutions. This AI software evaluates inspection data using advanced AI architectures and they will only be used to detect infrastructure defects. The AI system will respect every one of the EC ethical guidelines.

4.3. Guidelines for the impact assessment in Legal Aspect

The main applicable regulatory framework in respect of the ethical considerations is connected to the operation of unmanned vehicles. Nevertheless, this deliverable also explores how some of the SIMAR Uses Cases perform in Oil & Gas facilities, analysing the need to comply with ATEX certification and X-Ray legislation.

4.3.1. European Drone Regulation

The European Drone Regulation must be fulfilled during SIMAR project experiments. The platforms developed within the SIMAR project will be classified as either Open or Specific category and they must always comply with the regulations established in this regulation.

Since the refinery in France is in a no-fly zone (due to the criticality of the infrastructure) and only operations under the Specific category are authorised, this category applies to the Refinery UAV inspection use cases.

Analysing now each subcategory of operation, we can conclude that:

Open Category

Due to the nature of SIMAR mock-up tests and their location, in most of the cases the A3 subcategory applies. In this subcategory, three different types of UAS can be operated:

- C3 or C4 labelled drones.
- Private built.

The labelled drones require to pass through a conformity process with a homologated notified body. Since this process has a high cost, SIMAR UAS will be first operated as privately built, and in the future (exploitation/industrialisation stage), it could be certified to be C3 or C4 labelled.

Specific Category

Since SIMAR does not count with labelled drones since all the UAS are completely new, incorporating cutting edge technologies, most of the flights under the Specific category will be performed under the Operational authorisation option. Furthermore, as the SIMAR final scenario is a petrochemical plant, it will be considered under Specific category as well.

4.3.2. ATEX

The ATEX directive regards explosive atmospheres in refineries as a significant source of risk for which the equipment employed must be suitable. This regulatory framework is paramount because Refinery is the SIMAR Project's key use case. This regulation, on the other hand, was created with static and fixed equipment in mind. Because of the challenges in applying the ATEX directive to mobile systems, the Oil&Gas industry has begun to build emergency operations procedures to employ non-ATEX equipment in hazardous regions.

When a firm performs works on a refinery, there are two basic approaches: use ATEX-certified instruments or work under a hot-work permit using portable gas detectors in cooperation with emergency protocols. After studying this issue in depth (during the proposal definition, including workshops with ATEX certification experts from well-known certification companies), it was determined that the best method for handling this barrier in SIMAR, due to the time and financial limitations of the R&D project, is to use hot-work permits implementing emergency operational procedures.

Since 2016, CHEVRON has issued "Guidance Notes for Inspection Using Unmanned Aircraft Systems," which outline the minimal conditions that aerial robot equipment and crews must meet in order to execute operations inside a refinery. As a result, the SIMAR initiative will take a two-pronged approach:

- In order to reduce the risk of explosion while employing robotic systems in refineries, it will take into account best practices design recommendations for the Oil&Gas sector (including a number of ATEX criteria).
- It will conduct comprehensive safety assessments and develop emergency operations procedures to meet the needs of the refinery owners. To address the dangers connected with robotic system operations, this special safety procedure must be designed. In the context of this project, impacts on the design and capabilities of robotic systems should be anticipated. The following issues should be taken into account in particular:
 - On-board gas detector with real-time transmission.
 - Create an emergency procedure for "what if" gas detection:
 - i. In the case of an aerial robot, the robot will automatically fly away from the location.
 - ii. In the event of a crawling hybrid-robot, the robot fixes itself on the piping and the electricity is immediately turned off.
 - iii. In the event of a ground robot or crawler, the robot immediately stops, and the power is turned off.

Finally, it was stated that the SIMAR consortium will maintain record of the unmanned vehicles that would receive ATEX certification in order to consider any potential inputs while developing the SIMAR system.

4.3.3. X-Ray regulation

4.3.3.1. Spanish X-Ray Regulation

Understanding the legal aspects of operating X-ray equipment is crucial for ensuring safety and compliance with relevant regulations in the industrial technology field. Compliance with regulations governing X-ray equipment is of utmost importance, especially given its use in potentially hazardous environments, such as those prevalent in the oil and gas industry. To operate X-ray radiative facilities for industrial purposes, a comprehensive documentation process is imperative. This entails the meticulous preparation of technical documents, which constitute an integral part of the authorization request.

Furthermore, in the context of the SIMAR Project, where X-ray equipment is utilized in aerial inspections, specific safety measures have been implemented. Two distinct zones have been delineated, each signposted and marked to allow access only to authorized personnel. The first zone, extending up to 10 meters, permits entry only to the supervisor and the drone pilot responsible for operating the equipment. Beyond this, there is a second zone, spanning 30 meters, where access by the public is restricted. Additionally, all personnel within the facility will be informed of ongoing inspections.

Figure 2. Zone delimitation for x ray inspection

Professionals working with X-ray equipment are subject to exposure limits, which are meticulously defined by regulations to ensure protection against harmful radiation levels. As a precaution, all individuals operating within the facility are required to carry personal and non-transferable dosimeters. These dosimeters will undergo an annual review to verify correct dosing, with the facility supervisor maintaining an annual dosimeter record.

Moreover, the regulations specify the deployment of various real-time environmental radiation monitoring devices. In this context, a Digital Geiger Counter, model Digiliret 100, has been acquired and will be continuously positioned around the designated area. It will feature an audible alarm to alert in case of detecting radiation levels exceeding the preset threshold. This comprehensive approach aligns with the regulations' requirement for radiological protection measures within the facility, emphasizing the establishment of safety protocols to prevent radiation exposure to individuals present.

In addition to safety measures, comprehensive documentation encompasses the formulation of a meticulous plan outlining the process and frequency of equipment inspections within the facility. In this case, the equipment consists of a Litex generator and a FlatScan 15XS X-ray detector, both from Teledyne ICM. These components will undergo annual maintenance and review by Teledyne ICM. The Geiger counter will also undergo calibration every 5 years by the Polytechnic University of Catalonia, following ISO 4037 (2019) standards, with annual verification by Radiansa Consulting. Furthermore, the plan includes a detailed breakdown of personnel-related aspects, including the appointment of a supervisor and the designation of a facility manager.

In conclusion, comprehending and adhering to the legal aspects related to X-ray equipment operation is essential to maintain safety and regulatory compliance in industrial settings. This underscores a strong commitment to both safety and legal compliance in the utilization of such equipment.

4.3.3.2. French X-Ray Regulation

The current French regulations do not address drone fly equipped with an X-ray generator. This situation requires specific instruction and a dedicated assessment of the risks associated with this new practice.

Depending on the dose rate, risk mitigation actions may include:

- Wearing a personal dosimeter checked monthly by the administration
- Establishing a marked zone
- Periodic equipment checks
- Installing a Geiger counter in the area.

4.4. Guidelines for the impact assessment which applies to SIMAR Impact Scenario

To conclude the definition of the guidelines for carrying out the Impact Assessment, Table 4 outlines which of the defined SoEL standards and principles apply to each effect scenario. This will allow the Impact Assessment to be carried out while taking into account all of the relevant data protection standards (social), legal and ethical issues that apply to project outcomes and activities with a significant impact.

Table 4. Applicable SoEL requirements to each SIMAR Scenario

Impact Scenarios	Social	Ethical	Legal
Impact Scenario 1: Refinery – UAV (Visual Inspection)	GDPR	AI ACT principles	UAV regulation ATEX requirements
Impact Scenario 2: Refinery – UAV (X-Ray)	GDPR (if necessary)	AI ACT principles	UAV regulation ATEX requirements X-Ray regulation
Impact Scenario 3: Refinery - UAV (PEC)	GDPR (if necessary)	AI ACT principles	UAV regulation ATEX requirements X-Ray regulation

5. IMPACT ASSESSMENT METHODOLOGY

As previously mentioned, the methodology employed in this 2nd "Impact Assessment Report" follows the same approach outlined in D9.1 and consists of three key steps (refer to Figure 1):

1. **Impact assessment identification:** This step focuses on identifying potential risks associated with non-compliance with SoEL requirements. To facilitate this assessment, the SIMAR consortium has utilized various tools, including partner meetings, such as the one held on June 20th.
2. **Impact assessment analysis:** During this stage, the identified risks will undergo both quantitative and qualitative assessment, enabling a comprehensive understanding of their significance and potential impact.

3. Impact assessment evaluation and treatment: This step entails the development of a contingency plan to mitigate or minimize each identified risk, ensuring that adequate measures are in place to address any potential adverse effects.

By following these three steps, the SIMAR project aims to conduct a thorough and systematic assessment of the impacts and risks associated with non-compliance with SoEL requirements. This process enables the project team to proactively address any identified risks and develop appropriate mitigation strategies, ensuring the project's adherence to the defined standards and guidelines.

5.1. SoEL Impact Assessment Identification

An essential aspect of the impact assessment involves conducting a thorough and comprehensive risk identification and statement process. The impact assessment will specifically address key areas such as privacy and data protection, unmanned aerial vehicles, artificial intelligence, and novel technologies. Within each of these areas, the main risks related to the SoEL aspects of the SIMAR project will be identified and addressed based on the defined requirements. Each requirement represents a potential obstacle that the SIMAR project must overcome or ensure compliance with, both in the context of the project itself and through the deployment of any elements created within it.

To facilitate the identification of risks associated with non-compliance with SoEL requirements, the SIMAR consortium will conduct two workshops/meetings. The initial meeting held on June 20th served as a starting point for identifying risks for the SoEL Impact Assessment report. These meetings and workshops are essential as the project involves stakeholders from diverse sectors inside the consortium, including research and innovation partners, technological companies, SMEs, inspection and maintenance service providers, and infrastructure operators. Their participation is crucial for obtaining a comprehensive understanding of the SoEL impact assessment.

In the upcoming deliverable (D8.2), a new meeting will be organized and extended to a wider range of risks. These two meetings will address the expected applications of the SIMAR solution, ensuring alignment with SoEL principles.

5.2. SoEL Impact Assessment Analysis

SIMAR is a multidisciplinary project that includes many work streams that operate in diverse fields of competence. Therefore, it is essential for all project participants to carefully examine the meeting participants' comments to identify potential risks. Two specialized workshops including all partners will be conducted, taking into account their different areas of competence, to ensure agreement. To address each risk identified, the Impact Assessment report will also include the following kinds of questions:

- What is the probability of this risk occurring?
- What is the potential impact magnitude if this risk materializes?

5.3. SoEL Impact Assessment Evaluation and Treatment

The insights provided by each partner during the Impact Assessment analysis workshop, drawing on their specific expertise within the SIMAR project, will enable a comprehensive evaluation of whether the requirements related to the identified risks have been adequately addressed. These inputs will be utilized to generate an impact assessment report, which will document the measures taken thus far and determine their sufficiency in meeting the outlined requirements. In cases where the implemented measures are deemed insufficient, the evaluation report, developed through consultation with relevant partners, will propose additional steps to ensure compliance with identified requirements.

To facilitate the update of the Impact assessment evaluation and treatment, the following types of questions will be incorporated:

- What mitigation measures have already been implemented or will be implemented to minimize or avoid risks?
- Are there any remaining residual risks? If so, are they justified?

All the work conducted during these three stages will be thoroughly documented in the upcoming version of the Impact assessment report in deliverable D8.2.

6. CONCLUSIONS

The purpose of this deliverable is to present an overview of the ethical principles and relevant legal aspects pertaining to the primary technologies being developed within the SIMAR project, namely autonomous vehicles and artificial intelligence. Additionally, it addresses the topics of data protection and privacy. The aim is to equip SIMAR partners with essential knowledge that can be used as a reference point for evaluating the project's impact on societal, ethical, and legal considerations that have been identified.

Finally, this deliverable will serve as a starting point for the framework of deliverable D8.2 where the results of the proposed methodology will be shown.

After that, the reviewed SoEL aspects to address within SIMAR project are as follows:

- **Social aspects:** the main applicable legislation concerning privacy and data protection in all SIMAR countries is the GDPR. The access to the data collected must be restricted only to authorised personnel. Nothing of the provided personal data will be handled out to third parties. A Data Project Officer (DPO) must be appointed.
- **Ethical aspect:** Regarding the ethical aspects, the main applicable regulatory framework is related to the AI technologies, which is summarised in the "Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI" [9]. In addition, the EC has presented proposal for AI regulation the "AI ACT 2021", which ensures that AI developed and used within Europe aligns with EU values. These values encompass various aspects such as the supervision of human involvement, prioritization of safety, protection of privacy, promotion of transparency, prevention of discrimination, and consideration of social and environmental well-being. The AI SIMAR developments will be

designed to comply with the limited and minimal risks outlined in these regulations. Both documents have been analysed to set the ethical principles that must be respected in the development of artificial intelligence algorithms. The "Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI" establish that the AI development must respect for human autonomy, prevention of harm, fairness and explicability. The "AI ACT 2021" considers three main categories in which risks can be classified: Unacceptable, High and Limited and minimal. The AI SIMAR developments will be designed to comply with the limited and minimal risk. Currently, the negotiations among the EU countries is taking place and it is expected to achieve an agreement by the end of the year.

- **Legal aspect:** the main legal applicable regulation is related with the operation of Unmanned Vehicles. Concerning the UAV: the "European Drone regulation". In the SIMAR project, the aerial platforms developed will be within the categories "open" or "specific". In this deliverable, the operational requirements within each category have been described: in SIMAR, we work in A3 subcategory: Private Built in "open category" and in Operational authorization in "specific category". SIMAR aerial robots must always comply with the specifications and operational requirements defined in this regulation. In addition, a new policy instrument to validate new technologies and solutions without having to wait to have a complete regulation approved to start offering services and products using novel technologies has been analyzed: the "Regulatory Sandbox". This has been analyzed as an option to regulate the SIMAR developments related to novel technologies as AI, in one of the countries where the SIMAR solution will be implemented. In addition, mention that this deliverable has analyse the ATEX requirements. Due to the difficulties of applying ATEX directive to dynamic equipment, during the SIMAR experiments will be used hot-work permits, defined by the refinery. Finally, the SIMAR project also considers the legal framework pertaining to X-ray equipment usage. Compliance with X-ray equipment regulations, including those related to safety and radiation exposure limits, is crucial to ensure the project's adherence to legal requirements and the protection of personnel working with such equipment.

Finally, this deliverable remains an impact assessment methodology to be followed within the Impact Assessment Report (deliverable D8.2).

- **Impact assessment Identification:** To help the identification of possible risks related to non-compliance with SoEL requirements.
- **Impact assessment analysis:** The quantification and qualification of the risk identified in this new iteration.
- **Impact assessment evaluation and treatment:** A contingency plan will be defined to avoid/minimise each identified risk.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] European Union, "General Data Protection Regulation," 27 April 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32016R0679&from=ES>. [Accessed September 2023].
- [2] European Union, "Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union," 2016. [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=legisum:l33501>. [Accessed September 2023].
- [3] European Union, "2019/947 Rules and procedures for the operation of unmanned aircraft," 24 May 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32019R0947&from=EN>. [Accessed September 2023].
- [4] EASA, "Open Category - Civil Drones," [Online]. Available: <https://www.easa.europa.eu/domains/civil-drones/drones-regulatory-framework-background/open-category-civil-drones>. [Accessed September 2023].
- [5] European Commission, "ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE ACT," 21 April 2021. [Online]. Available: https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:e0649735-a372-11eb-9585-01aa75ed71a1.0001.02/DOC_1&format=PDF. [Accessed September 2023].
- [6] European Commission, "A European approach to artificial intelligence," [Online]. Available: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/european-approach-artificial-intelligence#A-European-approach-to-Artificial-Intelligence>. [Accessed September 2023].
- [7] European Commission, "White Paper on Artificial Intelligence: a European approach to excellence and trust," 19 February 2020. [Online]. Available: https://commission.europa.eu/publications/white-paper-artificial-intelligence-european-approach-excellence-and-trust_en. [Accessed September 2023].
- [8] McKinsey & Company, "What the draft European Union AI regulations mean for business," 10 August 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mckinsey.com/business-functions/quantumblack/our-insights/what-the-draft-european-union-ai-regulations-mean-for-business>. [Accessed September 2023].
- [9] European Commission, "Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI," 08 April 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>. [Accessed September 2023].

- [10] Aviación Digital, “SANDBOX: un banco de pruebas regulatorio dirigido a la innovación en la aviación y el transporte en general,” 24 April 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://aviaciondigital.com/sandbox-un-banco-de-pruebas-regulatorio-dirigido-a-la-innovacion-en-la-aviacion-y-el-transporte-en-general/?nowprocket=1>. [Accessed September 2023].
- [11] European Commission, “Better regulation' toolbox,” November 2021.
- [12] Financial Conduct Authority, “Regulatory Sandbox,” March 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.fca.org.uk/firms/innovation/regulatory-sandbox>. [Accessed September 2023].
- [13] Civil Aviation Authority, “Beyond Visual Line of Sight (BVLOS) operations of unmanned aircraft systems (UAS) in unsegregated airspace: Sandbox brief,” 1 August 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://publicapps.caa.co.uk/modalapplication.aspx?appid=11&mode=detail&id=9178>. [Accessed September 2023].
- [14] Civil Aviation Authority, “Regulatory sandbox guidance for the Future Flight Challenge,” 19 April 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://publicapps.caa.co.uk/modalapplication.aspx?appid=11&mode=detail&id=10357>. [Accessed September 2023].
- [15] THE EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT AND THE COUNCIL OF THE EUROPEAN UNION, “Data Protection Directive (95/46/EC),” 24 10 1995. [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:31995L0046>. [Accessed September 2023].
- [16] European Commission, “Equipment for potentially explosive atmospheres (ATEX),” [Online]. Available: https://single-market-economy.ec.europa.eu/sectors/mechanical-engineering/equipment-potentially-explosive-atmospheres-atex_en. [Accessed September 2023].
- [17] Official Journal of the European Union, “Directive 2014/34/EU,” February 2014. [Online]. Available: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2014/34/oj>. [Accessed September 2023].
- [18] Bell, B. (2004). Sustainable Bridges, D1.2 European Railway Bridge Demography, Contract No. TIP3-CT-2003-001653.